

E3.5 Final prototype of the inclusion of AIOps and distributed intelligence in the system

**Fecha de Publicación:
31/05/2024**

[6GENABLERS-AI]
[6GENABLERS]

**Programa de Universalización de
Infraestructuras Digitales para la
Cohesión - 6G I+D**

Financiado por la Unión Europea
NextGenerationEU

GOBIERNO
DE ESPAÑA

Plan de Recuperación,
Transformación
y Resiliencia

Paquete de Trabajo (PT)	PT3
Líder del PT	i2CAT
Editor Principal	Juan Sebastian Camargo
Contribuyentes	Hatim Chergui, Shuaib Siddiqui
Nivel de diseminación	PU
Tipo	RE

Nivel de diseminación

PU	Publico
PP	Restringido a otros participantes del programa
RE	Restringido a un grupo especificado por el consorcio
CO	Confidencial solo para miembros del consorcio

Tipo

PR	Prototipo
RE	Reporte
SP	Especificación
TO	Herramienta
OT	Otro

Histórico de versiones del documento				
versión	Autor	Estado	Fecha	Comentarios
v1.0	Juan Sebastian Camargo		31/05/2024	

Table of Contents

Table of Contents.....	3
List of Tables.....	4
List of Figures.....	5
List of Acronyms.....	6
1 Introduction.....	7
2 Logical description.....	8
3 Configuration.....	10
4 Usage.....	11
5 Conclusion.....	13

List of Tables

List of Figures

Figure 1 Kubeflow Pipelines logic structure with Control Loop.....8

Figure 2 Kubeflow Pipelines final structure with Control Loop.....12

List of Acronyms

3D	Three Dimension
AI	Artificial Intelligence
AIOps	AI Operations
AR	Augmented Reality
CD	Continuous Delivery
CI	Continuous Integration
6DoF	Six Degrees of Freedom
FPS	Frame per Second
HD	High Definition
HTC	Holographic-Type Communications
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
MEC	Multi-access Edge Computing
ML	Machine Learning
MLOps	Machine Learning Operations
NFV	Network Function Virtualization
NR	New Radio
QoE	Quality of Experience
RAN	Radio Access Network
SoA	State-of-the-Art
TD	Technological Domain
UE	User Equipment
UNICO	Universalización de Infraestructuras Digitales para la Cohesión
VNF	Virtual Network Function
VR	Virtual Reality
XR	Extended Reality

1 Introduction

Based on the architecture exposed in Deliverable D3.6.2 “Final design for distributed AI operations in 6G”, a closed control loop is necessary to actively monitor the confidence level that the ML model is producing.

Whenever that confidence level is below a certain threshold, the ML model should be re-trained again with new data. The need to re-train the model could come for several reasons: the hidden patterns of the data could and actually change over time, leaving the previously trained models less effective. Additionally, new data unfamiliar to the model might be used, that was not present at the moment of the training.

As the environment changes, a model's performance may degrade if it continues to operate on outdated assumptions. Regularly evaluating and re-training the model ensures that it continues to perform optimally by aligning its predictions with current realities. Without re-training, models can become stale, meaning they no longer provide the best possible predictions based on the available data. This can lead to poor decision-making in critical applications.

In this deliverable we are going to describe how the Closed Control Loop works in the MLOPS process, using Kubeflow Pipelines as the main MLOPS platform.

2 Logical description

The provided code is a machine learning pipeline designed to automate the process of obtaining a dataset, preprocessing it, training a model, checking the model's confidence, and potentially retraining the model if its performance does not meet a specified threshold. This pipeline is implemented using Kubeflow, a platform for deploying, orchestrating, and running machine learning workflows on Kubernetes.

We have defined six basic pipeline blocks in the architecture, with a closed control loop between the Pre-Processing Dataset block and the Confidence Checking block. This structure can be seen in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Kubeflow Pipelines logic structure with Control Loop

The core components are briefly explained as follows:

Obtain Dataset: This component is responsible for obtaining and preparing the dataset. It downloads a CSV file from a specified URL, processes it and normalizes it using data manipulation techniques and then, the processed features and labels are saved and are ready to be used in the following steps.

Preprocess Dataset: After the initial data acquisition, this component splits the dataset into training and testing subsets. These subsets are stored separately, indicating that the data will be used following a typical train-test evaluation of machine learning models.

Model Building: Here, a model is constructed using TensorFlow and the logical tensor network (LTN) framework. The model follows the typical multiple dense layer architecture and is saved for training.

Training: This component loads the previously built model and training dataset to train the model. The training process is iterative, adjusting model weights based on predefined loss functions. The model would need to reach a previously fixed threshold level before the training is completed.

Confidence Checking: Post-training, this component evaluates the model's performance by calculating how confidently the model can predict below a certain threshold. This involves loading the trained model, applying SHAP (SHapley Additive exPlanations) for interpretability, and determining if the predictions meet the expected confidence level.

Exposed Model: When the model is deemed adequate to be put in production, it could be exposed so the other interfaces can interact with said model. This is where the inference phase takes place.

3 Configuration

The retraining stage is a structured approach to improving the model's performance when its confidence metric is unsatisfactory. Initially, a base model is built and trained using the provided training dataset. This training involves defining a neural network with specific layers and activation functions, followed by an optimization process where the model learns to make accurate predictions through multiple epochs.

If the initial training does not yield a confident model, the retraining stage kicks in. The retraining process involves several key steps:

- **Re-initialization:** The model architecture remains the same, but the model is retrained with the same dataset.
- **Gradient Adjustment:** The training process involves adjusting the gradients to minimize a loss function, which includes both the model's prediction errors and a statistical measure (like the cumulative distribution function) that helps quantify the prediction accuracy.
- **Repeated Evaluation:** After each retraining session, the model's confidence is checked again. This involves using a deep learning explainer tool (like SHAP) to understand the model's predictions better and to identify where the model might be falling short.
- **Iterative Improvement:** This process iterates up to a specified maximum number of attempts. Each iteration aims to incrementally improve the model's confidence until it meets the required threshold, or the iterations are exhausted.

This retraining loop is vital in scenarios where the initial model does not perform well, ensuring that the model is rigorously tested and improved before being finalized for deployment. By embedding this control mechanism in the pipeline, the code ensures robust model performance and reliability, crucial for scientific and industrial applications where model accuracy and confidence are paramount.

```
with dsl.ParallelFor([i for i in range(max_attempts)]) as i:
    with Condition(confidence.outputs["confidence_metric"] < confidence_threshold):
        training_task = training(
            function_f_artifact = model_building_task.outputs["function_f"],
            x_full_artifact = dataset.outputs["x_full_artifact"],
            y_full_artifact = dataset.outputs["y_full_artifact"],
        )
        confidence_task = confidence_checking(
            trained_model = training_task.outputs["model_trained"],
            x_test_artifact = preprocessing.outputs["x_test_artifact"],
            x_train_artifact = preprocessing.outputs["x_train_artifact"],
            y_test_artifact = preprocessing.outputs["y_test_artifact"],
        )
```

4 Usage

By using this snippet in conjunction with the other previously explained code (For more information please refer to deliverable “E3.2 Intermediate prototype of the inclusion of AIOps in the system”, we are finally able to execute the entire pipeline with a closed loop control, the final topology is the following:

Figure 2 Kubeflow Pipelines final structure with Control Loop

5 Conclusion

We have integrated successfully the use of Kubeflow Pipelines in our architecture. Kubeflow Pipelines offer a scalable framework that supports the development and deployment of AI models necessary for managing 6G networks. They provide a robust platform for iterating on machine learning models, allowing for continuous improvement and adaptation as network technologies evolve and new challenges arise. This scalability is crucial for future-proofing the networks and ensuring they can evolve with advancing technology and changing user needs.

In conclusion, the integration of closed control loops and Kubeflow Pipelines into the development of 6G network architectures aligns perfectly with the objectives of 6GEnablers-AI, optimizing network functions, dynamically composing services, and utilizing intelligent telemetry. These technologies not only support the complex requirements of modern networks but also ensure they are equipped to handle future demands efficiently and effectively. The strategic application of these advanced technologies is fundamental to achieving the holistic management and orchestration of network resources and services, paving the way for the successful implementation and operation of next-generation network infrastructures.